

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D9.2

Website

July 2021

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
ups	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
RMC-C&E	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
kcl	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UoE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
H2020	Horizon 2020
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
PC	Project Coordinator
TBD	To Be Decided
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as a reference document among MES-CoBraD consortium partners as well as other researchers and members of the scientific community, as it presents and documents the design, implementation, and deployment of the MES-CoBraD project website. The deliverable can also serve as a guideline for research projects that are seeking to explore options for efficient dissemination through a website, providing ideas of how information could be promoted and organized through a dedicated project website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report mainly outlines the design, implementation, and deployment process of the MES-CoBraD Website to be used for the Communication and Dissemination purposes of the project and in accordance with the corresponding C&D plan. The main elements of the Website will be explained, alongside with the responsibilities of the consortium where possible.

The material presented on the website and the social media accounts will be regularly updated by the MES-CoBraD consortium in alignment with the D9.1 “Dissemination & Communication Plan-MES-CoBraD” deliverable.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report, and the website, which can be accessed at <https://mes-cobrad.eu/>.

Executive Summary

The D9.2 report presents and documents the design, implementation, and deployment of the MES-CoBraD project website. The MES-CoBraD website is available at the following address: <https://mes-cobrad.eu/>.

Following most recent practices and principles for web design, the MES-CoBraD website is presented in a modern, yet minimalistic & user-friendly approach, incorporating in detail the project's concept and objectives, presenting the relevant material, and hosting a dedicated section for news and events.

As described in the initial communication strategy, presented in D9.1 "Dissemination & Communication Plan-MES-CoBraD", social media will be utilised as a core communication mechanism during the MES-CoBraD project implementation.

The project's website along with social media accounts will be constantly updated, allowing for the proper dissemination of the project results and the communication with the general public and for presenting project results, publications, news, events and overall progress, expecting also participation from partners, related projects, and the broader community, until the completion of the project.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D9.2 is part of WP9, entitled “Raising awareness, dissemination and communication”, and in particular of Task 9.3 “Online presence”. The project website has been developed and is hosted at <https://www.mes-cobrad.eu/>. The MES-CoBraD Platform upon being developed, is expected to have an impact in the relevant fields and serve as a mean to keep the Website alive and current.

1.1 PURPOSE

The project website, in line with the MES-CoBraD Platform, will serve as the main front to present and disseminate the project’s results but also to be a reference site containing useful dissemination material as well as links related to the purposes of real-world approved therapies that are associated with improved clinical prognosis and psychosocial well-being in CoBraD, in parallel to identifying whether any approved therapies are associated with worse prognosis in CoBraD. The project’s progress and results will be published online in our website. The development of the website is of great importance for the effective promotion of the MES-CoBraD project including results, and stakeholder engagement. The website includes information about the project, the consortium composition, objectives and mission, organisation, Stakeholder Council, and the MES-CoBraD Platform. It also includes agendas of events; all communication, dissemination and exploitation material; project deliverables; and visualised materials (infographics, videos, etc.).

2 MES-COBRA D WEBSITE

The domain name of the project's website is <https://mes-cobrad.eu/>. It contains the name of the project, with an EU extension denoting its European Origin. The selected wording fully complies with the requirement of a successful domain, being short, descriptive and easy to remember with direct reference to the project.

The website is built upon the latest version of the Drupal operating system (version 8.0), which is a free, open-source content management system (CMS).

For measuring the website traffic and monitoring the visitors' behaviour, a connection with the Google Analytics service has been established and configured. The data insights coming from the MES-CoBraD website can be accessed directly from the Google Analytics interface and will enable us to improve the site and project notability.

2.1 DESIGN

The MES-CoBraD website design follows the latest trends in web design, having also in mind the special characteristics of the project's objectives.

The MES-CoBraD website exhibits the following properties:

- › Operates under a modern, clean and light interface, with contrasting project relevant colours for the text and background to make reading easier on the eye and with vibrant colours being only used for emphasis (e.g. links) where necessary.
- › Easy navigation to content through a comprehensive structure that is implemented both on the front page and the various menus.
- › Utilises a clean and modern typography throughout the website and all sections, with large fonts that are easier to read.
- › Implements a responsive design, making the website respond and adapt to the user's input and environment, based on their device (desktop/laptop computer, tablet or mobile/smartphone) and screen size.

Overall, the MES-CoBraD website is built on modern web design principles, focusing on usability, accessibility and intuitive navigation.

A preview of the website's front page is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 MES-CoBraD website Home Page

2.2 STRUCTURE AND CONTENT

The main menu links aid in the site navigation and are located at the top part of every website page. This is a two-level navigation menu that aims to guide the visitor in a simple and intuitive manner with dropdown submenus. Currently, it consists of the following items and will be constantly updated to comply with the project needs:

Figure 2 MES-CoBraD website structure (site map)

- › The Project logo on the top left corner of the webpage serves as a “Home” button and returns the visitor to the home page.
- › The “About” menu-item includes the project overview description and 3 more sections presenting the Expected Project Impact, the Partners and the Advisory Board.
- › The “Pilots” menu-item presents the Pilot Use Cases (PUC) to be executed under the MES-CoBraD project.
- › The “Solution” menu-item included 4 sections, presenting the concept, the technical architecture of the project and the possible application scenarios.
- › The “Platform” menu-item links to the MES-CoBraD integrated Platform.
- › “News & Events” menu item contains links to all posts about news concerning the project, as well as events scheduled for MES-CoBraD that partners will attend or have attended. It is the main place for those visitors that would like to stay in touch with the progress of MES-CoBraD.
- › “Communication” includes the sub-category Media where all online media related material regarding the project can be found.
- › The “Materials” menu-item links to Zenodo and OpenAIR repositories where all published material related to the project is available.
- › The “Synergies” menu-item contains links to project joint activities, initiatives and organisations related to the project's work and results.

2.3 MAIN ELEMENTS OF THE WEBSITE PAGES

The MES-CoBraD page consists of three basic design parts:

- › The Header located at the top
- › The Footer at the bottom
- › The Content in between

2.3.1 HEADER

The Header as presented in Figure 3 below, contains the MES-CoBraD logo, the navigation menu, the search facility, and a pop-up container-menu in the right including the “About” synopsis and link to all project social media.

Figure 3 MES-CoBraD website header

2.3.2 FOOTER

The Footer is presented in Figure 4 below and includes two sections. The one on the left presents a statement that the project is funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. The right section provides links to the project’s Social Media accounts/pages.

Below both parts a link to the Privacy & Cookies Policy page is included. An arrow button is hovering on the bottom right corner redirecting the user to the top of the page as part of the responsive design.

Figure 4 MES-CoBraD website footer

2.3.3 HOME PAGE

The website’s Home page consists of sections, as shown in Figure 1 of this document, and aims in attracting the visitor’s interest and providing information about the various aspects of the MES-CoBraD.

2.3.3.1 1st Section: Header

The header is analysed in Section 2.3.1 of this document.

2.3.3.2 2nd Section: Slider

The slider acts as a slideshow, with manual navigation between the slides available to the user through arrow buttons. The slides are clickable and refer to specific sections of the website.

Figure 5 MES-CoBraD website slider

2.3.3.3 3rd Section: About

This section includes the about page with a set of navigation buttons redirecting the visitor to “Overview”, “Expected Impact”, “Partners” and “Advisory Board” pages.

2.3.3.4 4th Section: The MES-CoBraD Solution

This section redirects the visitor to the MES-CoBraD solution page.

2.3.3.5 5th Section: Subscribe to Newsletter Banner

A pop-up linked page linked to the “Subscribe” button in the right side of the banner allows for the subscription to the MES-CoBraD newsletter.

Figure 6 MES-CoBraD website Subscribe section

Figure 7 MES-CoBraD website Subscribe pop-up page

2.3.3.6 6th Section: News & Events

This section titles and short summaries of selected important events and other project-related news. Below each news summary a “Read more” clickable button redirects to the corresponding MES-CoBraD news page which is loaded and displayed.

Figure 8 MES-CoBraD home page News & Events section

2.3.3.7 7th Section: Footer

The footer is analysed in Section 2.3.2 of this document.

2.3.4 OTHER PAGES

The rest of the pages included in the website, also referred as “inside pages” are categorised into “static content” pages and “dynamic content” pages. The static content pages usually contain information not

meant to be altered frequently. Typical examples of such pages in the MES-CoBraD project website are the “Partners”, “The Concept”, “Architecture” and more. The dynamic content pages contain information that changes frequently, such as the “News & Events” page and therefore are designed appropriately.

An example of a static page is shown in Figure 9 and an example of a dynamic page in Figure 10.

Figure 9 MES-CoBraD website static page example

Figure 10 MES-CoBraD website dynamic page example

3 SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

MES-CoBraD has established its presence in three social networks listed in the table below, along with their respective web address.

Social Network	MES-CoBraD account	URL
	@MESCoBraD	https://twitter.com/MESCoBraD
	mes-cobrad	https://www.linkedin.com/company/mes-cobrad/
	mescobrad	https://www.facebook.com/mescobrad/

Table 1 MES-CoBraD Social Media accounts

The footer, included in all MES-CoBraD website pages, presents links to the above-mentioned social media accounts. These will be used throughout the duration of the project to engage users and create traffic to the website.

In the following sections the MES-CoBraD social media account pages are presented.

3.1 TWITTER

Figure 11 MES-CoBraD Twitter account page

3.2 LINKEDIN

Figure 12 MES-CoBraD LinkedIn account page

3.3 FACEBOOK

Figure 13 MES-CoBraD Facebook account page

4 NEXT STEPS

- › In late 2022 the MES-CoBraD platform will be launched and the corresponding link on the website will be activated.
- › The website will be continuously updated, enhanced, and improved with new material as the project evolves.

